

Migration assessment and the ‘threshold of toxicological concern’ applied to the safe design of an acrylic adhesive for food-contact laminates

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ABSTRACT

The suitability of an acrylic adhesive used on food packaging was studied. Six potential migrants were identified using GC-MS and UPLC-QTOF. Five compounds were intentionally added (2-butoxyethanol and 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5-decyne-4,7-diol 10 (TMDD) and TMDD ethoxylates). One of the compounds identified as 2-(12-(methacryloyloxy) dodecyl)malonic acid was a non-intentionally added substance (NIAS), which could be a methyl methacrylate derivative. A migration study from multilayers containing paper–adhesive–film was carried out. The films used were polyethylene (PE), polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate, polylactic acid (PLA) and Ecovio F2223®, which is a mixture of biodegradable polyester with PLA. All the non-volatile compounds, including the identified NIAS, migrated into the dry food simulant Tenax®. Five surfactants based on TMDD were found to migrate from all laminates into Tenax at levels from 0.05 to 0.6 mg kg⁻¹. The results showed that the lowest migration (0.01 mg kg⁻¹ for 2-(12-(methacryloyloxy)dodecyl) malonic acid to 0.07 for TMDD mg kg⁻¹) occurred when the compounds passed through PLA, demonstrating its functional barrier properties to these compounds. In contrast, PE showed the worst barrier properties to these compounds. To evaluate the migration results, the threshold of toxicological concern strategy was applied. The migration values of the surfactant identified were above 0.09 mg kg⁻¹. Thus, it was decided to remove this surfactant from the formulation.

Introduction

The range of applications for adhesives in food packaging is very wide. They are used to form multilayers using a combination of substrates, to form the geometric shape of the package, and to adhere labels onto packages or even directly onto the food. As yet there are no European Union (EU)-harmonised regulations specific for adhesives intended to be used in food-contact materials (FCMs), so they must comply with the general European regulations common for all FCMs. These regulations are GMP Regulation (EC) 2023/2006 (EC 2006) and Framework Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 that establishes the following: materials and articles, including active and intelligent materials and articles, should be manufactured in compliance with good manufacturing practice so that, under normal or foreseeable conditions of use, they do not transfer their constituents to food in quantities that could: (1) endanger human health; or (2) bring about an unacceptable change in the composition of the food; or (3) bring about a deterioration in the organoleptic characteristics thereof (EC 2004). Besides, there are EU member states’ regulations/recommendations on food-contact adhesives such as the Spanish Royal Decree 847/2011 (Ministerio español de sanidad 2011), the Ministerial Decree of 21 March 1973 (Sanità 1973) and German BfR Recommendation XXVIII (Risikobewertung 2010). Because of that and in order to comply with the European regulation it is essential to study the migration to food or food simulants. Firstly, it has to be considered that testing of the pure adhesive will overestimate migration, as contributing factors to migration are not sufficiently considered (curing times and conditions, interaction with substrates,

barrier properties of substrates, ratio of adhesive amount to food packaged weight). Furthermore, both intentionally added substances (IASs) and non-intentionally added substances (NIASs) could migrate. NIASs can be generated by contamination, degradation products and impurities but also by the reaction between compounds in substrates (Svenson 2002; Bradley & Castle 2006; Canellas et al. 2010b, 2012, 2015a, 2015b; Nerin et al. 2013; Koster et al. 2015). Regulation 10/2011/EU states that any potential health risk in the final material or article arising from reaction and degradation products should be assessed by the manufacturer in accordance with internationally recognized scientific principles on risk assessment. The evaluation of NIASs should be extended along the supply chain of non-plastic FCMs including adhesives. As a result of all that, adhesives have to be evaluated under real-use conditions. Moreover, in order to identify the potential migrants, it is necessary to analyse the adhesive alone and the adhesive in the packaging to detect both IASs and NIASs produced by the interaction of the adhesive and the rest of the packaging. There are many adhesive systems used for food-contact applications: polyurethane adhesives predominantly used for lamination of polymer films and polymer films with aluminium foil, adhesives based on natural polymers such as dextrans or starches used for secondary/tertiary packaging or paper and cardboard packaging, adhesives based on vinyl acetate or ethylene vinyl acetate copolymers are used for paper and cardboard packagings, adhesives based on acrylic polymers used for packaging of dry foodstuff, cold seals used as a seam sealing application on film and paper, heat seals used for film and foil substrates for trays and cup lids and hot-melt adhesives used for paper and cardboard for dry foodstuff and for tertiary and secondary packaging (FEICA 2016). The various components that can constitute an adhesive formulation include: base resin or binder, catalyst or hardeners, accelerators, inhibitors, retarders, solvents, thickeners, diluents, extenders, fillers, carriers, plasticisers, flexibilisers, tackifiers, film formers, antioxidants, anti-hydrolysis, antifungals, soaps, surfactants and wetting agents (Petrie 2006). On account of the wide range of adhesive applications in FCMs and the complexity of the chemistry, no unified testing conditions can be defined for testing adhesives in FCMs. Therefore, in many cases the conditions defined in Regulation 10/2011/EU (EC 2011) for plastics cannot be applied literally. Thus, each single case has to be studied in order to do the migration assays trying to simulate the real conditions. In addition, most of the migrants are not listed in Regulation 10/2011/EU. Plastics Europe has proposed a toxicological assessment. Based on the TDI and the European assumption that a 60-kg person consumes 1 kg of food per day, a self-derived specific migration limit (SML) for a substance can be calculated. There are two approaches to determine the TDI: based on toxicological studies or in case it is not possible, based on the threshold of toxicological concern (TTC) concept (Plastics Europe 2014). The TTC methodology is based on a decision-tree approach that uses information on the molecular structure of a substance to assign the substance to one of a number of classes according the Cramer decision tree (Cramer et al. 1978). Each Cramer class is allocated to an exposure limit. Certain substance classes are exempt from the TTC concept, either because they were not part of the toxicological database used to derive the thresholds, or because they are of high toxicological concern and warrant a safety assessment based on substance-specific data. The TTC approach is not applicable when compound-specific assessment and toxicity data are available or are required under existing regulations. The EFSA considers it as a valid screening tool, based on scientific risk assessment principles, to assess low-dose chemical exposures, and to distinguish those for which further data are required to assess the human health risk from those with no appreciable risk (Canady et al. 2013; Dewhurst & Renwick 2013; EFSA 2016). In this work, the suitability of the use of an acrylic adhesive for FCMs was studied. Firstly the

identification of potential migrants was carried out and then a migration study and an evaluation of the risk derived from it, applying the strategy previously described, were undertaken.

Materials and methods

Samples and reagents

A water-based acrylic adhesive was selected for the study. The adhesive was supplied by Samtack (Barcelona, Spain). It is normally used for the production of laminates based on a broad variety of films and papers. These laminates are part of food packages like bakery trays, boxes for sandwiches, bread packaging, etc. The materials used to form the laminates were: inorganic-coated mechanical pulp paper weighing 82 g m⁻², low-density polyethylene (LDPE) 40 µm, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) 12 µm, bi-oriented polypropylene (BOPP) 20 µm, polylactic acid (PLA) 20 µm and Ecovio® F2223 40 µm which is a biodegradable polyester for compostable film containing 32% of renewable resources due to its content of PLA. All these films and paper were suitable for food-contact applications. The multilayers were prepared applying 20 g m⁻² of adhesive over the plastic film. They were supplied by the adhesives company.

The following multilayers were built by gluing paper with the plastic films: paper-adhesive-LDPE, paper-adhesive-PET, paper-adhesive-BOPP, paper-adhesive-PLA and paper-adhesive-Ecovio.

The following reagents were purchased from Sigma- Aldrich Química S.A (Madrid, Spain): 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl- 5-decyne-4,7-diol, adipic acid, 2-methyl-2-isothiazol-3-one, 1,2-benzisothiazol-3(2H)-one, mono- 2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl succinate and ethoxy ethanol. HPLC-MS quality methanol purity grade 99.9%, acetonitrile purity grade 99.9% and ultra-LC/MS reagent grade water were supplied by J. T. Baker (Deventer, the Netherlands). Formic acid eluent additive for LC-MS purity grade 98–100% was supplied by Scharlab, S.L. The Lab Sourcing Group, Barcelona.

Sample preparation and migration tests

The migration study was done with poly(2,6-diphenylp- phenylene oxide) (Tenax®) as simulant E (for dry foods), according to table 1 of Regulation (EU) 10/2011 following the procedure optimised in previous works (Canellas et al. 2010a; Aznar et al. 2011; Vera et al. 2011). The cut-outs of each laminate, 5 × 5 cm in size, were placed in Petri dishes and covered with 1 g of Tenax forming a uniform layer (4 g Tenax dm⁻² laminate in accordance with UNE-EN 14338; AENOR 2004). The objective of the work was to study the migration from the adhesive through the substrates. Then Tenax was applied on both sides of each laminate. This system was kept in the oven at 40°C for 10 days according to annex V of Regulation (EU) 10/2011 which establishes these conditions for contact times between 3 and 30 days, and contact temperatures between 20 and 40°C. After that, it was extracted two consecutive times with 3.4 ml of methanol. The total solution was concentrated under a stream of N₂ to 200 µl. Finally, the extracts were analysed by GC-MS and UPLC-QTOF. Three replicates of each laminate and substrate were studied.

In order to identify if the migrants come from the adhesive, solutions of the adhesive were prepared. A total of 100 g of acetonitrile were added to 1 g of adhesive. The polymer precipitated and the solution was filtered. Then 1 µl of this solution was analysed by GC-MS and 5 µl UPLC-Q-TOF. Moreover, the laminates prepared with the adhesive were extracted with acetonitrile and analysed by the same techniques.

Instrumentation

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry single quadrupole (GC-MS)

The equipment used was a CTC Analytics CombiPal autosampler coupled to an Agilent 6890N GC with an MS 5975B detector (all Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA). The capillary column used was an HP-5MS (30 m × 0.25 μm × 250 μm) from Agilent Technologies (Madrid, Spain). The oven programme was as follows: 40°C for 2 min, at rate of 10°C min⁻¹ up to 300°C, maintained for 2 min. The injection type was splitless and the helium flow was 1 ml min⁻¹. The acquisition was done in electron-impact ionisation (EI). The mass detector was set at SCAN mode (in the range m/z 45–350). NIST 08 mass spectral search program version 2.0 was used for the identification of the compounds.

Ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry quadrupole time-of-flight (UPLC-QTOF)

Chromatography was carried out in an AcquityTM system using an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column of 17 μm particle size (2.1 mm × 100 mm), both from Waters (Milford, MA, USA). Chromatography was carried out at 0.3 ml min⁻¹ column flow and the column temperature was 35°C. The gradient used here was 5–95% methanol (0–10 min) and the volume of sample injected was 5 μl. The detector consisted of an atmospheric pressure ionisation (API) source with an electrospray interface (ESI) coupled to an MS consisting of a hexapole, a quadrupole, a collision cell and a time of flight analyser (QTOF) Xevo G2 from Waters.

The electrospray probe was set in both positive (ESI+) and negative (ESI-) modes. The corona voltage was 2.5 kV for (ESI+) and 0.5 kV for (ESI-), the sampling cone voltage was optimised between 20 and 50 V, finally 30 V was selected for the screening because more peaks were detected. Nitrogen was FOOD ADDITIVES & CONTAMINANTS: PART A 1723 used as a desolvation gas, the flow was 500 l h⁻¹ at 400°C, the cone gas flow was 20 l h⁻¹. MSE mode was selected for the acquisition; collision ramp energy from 5 to 30 V was used. The mass range considered was 10–1200 Da. Data were collected in centroid mode and the sensitivity analyser mode was selected. The accuracy and reproducibility of all the analyses were guaranteed by using a lockspray. Leucine-enkephalin was employed as the lock mass at a concentration of 2 ng ml⁻¹ in water-acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid and a flow rate of 5 μl min⁻¹. MassLynx v.4.1 software (Waters) was used to analyse the samples.

Results and discussion

Identification of migrants

In this work, non-targeted analysis of the adhesive was carried out in order to identify all the components that are included in the adhesive before studying their migration. Moreover, laminates were also extracted in order to study the possibility of formation of NIASs due to the interaction of the substrates and the adhesive.

In the first place, the identification of the volatile compounds in the adhesive was carried out by GCMS. An NIST mass spectral library search provided a list of matched chemical compounds from the library. Then, standards of the compounds were analysed for confirmatory purposes. Only one compound, 2-butoxyethanol, was detected. This adhesive has been processed after its production in order to minimise the volatiles to obtain a suitable food-contact adhesive.

This compound is a glycol ether with modest surfactant properties. It is also used as a solvent in acrylic resin formulations (Karsa 1990). No NIAs were found on the laminates by the interaction of adhesives with substrates.

UPLC-QTOF was used for the identification of nonvolatile compounds. This technique provides molecular fragmentation combined with mass accuracy in order to elucidate the molecular structure that could lead to the identification of the compounds. Conditions used for the acquisition were explained previously. The chromatogram was acquired in MSE mode. MSE mode is a method of data acquisition that involves the rapid switching between two energy conditions. Then two functions are obtained, one corresponding with the acquisition without collision energy, where we try to obtain a molecular formula through the accurate mass obtained. The other function is the result of applying the collision energy ramp (5–30 V). Here we obtain fragments in this function that are used to try to match them with the candidate proposed in order to confirm it.

Figure 1 shows the chromatograms obtained by UPLC-QTOF for the adhesive extract, Tenax blank extract and Tenax extract coming from the migration assay of the multilayer made with paper and PE (PE side). The first step of the work was to study the adhesive in order to identify the compounds. The following accurate masses: 249.1839, 293.2098, 337.2354 and 381.2612 Da were found in the spectra obtained from the peaks on the chromatogram from 6.15 to 6.50 min. We found out that these masses corresponded to the sodium adducts of the monomer 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5-decyne-4,7-diol (TMDD) and the polymers 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5-decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate $n = 1$ $m = 0$, TMDD ethoxylate $n = 1$ $m = 1$ and TMDD ethoxylate $n = 2$ $m = 1$. These compounds are NIAs, as they are surfactants used in water-based adhesives (Florio & Miller 2004; Ash & Ash 2007). Moreover, the spectrum of the peak at 6.79 min was extracted, the accurate mass was obtained (379.2101 Da) and the elemental composition was proposed by taking into account the isotopic pattern and the mass tolerance set at 3 mDa. Several candidate compounds were proposed with the help of the databases www.chemspider.com (Echegoyen et al. 2016) and www.scifinder.org (Society) and a bibliographic search. In order to confirm one candidate, the software MassFragment (Waters) was used. It uses chemically intelligent algorithms to see if the fragments obtained experimentally match with the fragments of the candidate proposed. Figure 2 shows the fragments obtained experimentally and the molecule fragments that match with them. The substance was identified as 2-(12-(methacryloyloxy)dodecyl)malonic acid. This compound is an NIA. It could be a derivative of methyl methacrylate (Sandler et al. 1998; Wypych 2016). No neo-formed compounds were found on the laminates by the interaction of adhesives with substrates.

Figure 1. Chromatograms obtained by the technique UPLC-MS/Q-TOF for Tenax blank extract, Tenax extract coming from the migration assay of the multilayer made of paper and PE (PE side) and the adhesive extract.

Figure 2. High-energy spectrum of the compound 2-(12-(methacryloyloxy)dodecyl)malonic acid.

Migration results

The adhesive was used for the manufacture of several multilayers using the substrates described above. These films were selected since they are the most common plastics films used for the kind of packaging in which the adhesive is applied according to the

data supplied by the adhesive company. Moreover, a thin paper (coated paper weighing 82 g m^{-2}) was selected for the study in order to use it as the worst-case migration scenario since thicker paper or even cardboard is used for building the laminates. Functional barriers are multilayer structures deemed to prevent migration of some chemicals released by FCMs into food (Feigenbaum et al. 2005). The objective of the study was to evaluate the functional barrier effect to the substances identified in the adhesive of each substrate in order to assess the optimal plastic film in terms of food-contamination risk. Since all the multilayers contained paper, Tenax was selected as a food simulant for migration studies following the indications described in both Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 and UNE-EN 14338 (AENOR 2001). Figure 3 shows the migration results (mg compound kg^{-1} simulant) obtained from the migration of the adhesive compounds through each material.

Figure 3. Migration results obtained from the migration of the adhesive compounds through each material.

The volatile compound identified, 2-butoxyethanol, migrated below the LOD (0.1 mg kg^{-1}). The LODs of the compounds were 0.01 mg kg^{-1} for 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5-decyne-4,7-diol (TMDD), 0.01 mg kg^{-1} for TMDD ethoxylated and 0.02 mg kg^{-1} for 2-(12-(methacryloyloxy) docecyl)malonic acid. The main advantage of the strategy followed here, identifying the IAS and NIAS for the adhesive and then studying their migration, is that we have a higher concentration of the compounds in the adhesive than in the migration extract. If we were to attempt to identify the compounds directly in the migration extract, we would have a lower concentration of the compounds and maybe some of them would not be detected in the migration extract because they would be under their LOD. Moreover, this strategy allows us to distinguish between NIASs formed in the adhesive and possible NIASs formed by the interaction of the adhesive and the substrates. As expected, migration of the compounds depended on the material they have to pass through. It is interesting to point out that two bioplastics have been evaluated in this work since these kinds of multilayers have been little studied (Canellas et al. 2015b). The results showed that the lowest migration occurred when the compounds pass through PLA, one of the bioplastics studied (migration levels ranging from 0.01 to 0.07 mg kg^{-1}). Although it is known that PLA has poor barrier properties to oxygen or carbon dioxide

(Farah et al. 2016; Svagan et al. 2012), it has good barrier properties to these compounds. In fact, it has been demonstrated in this work that PLA has the better barrier properties to these compounds of all the polymers studied. On the contrary, PE and Ecovio showed the worst barrier properties. The compounds migrating from the adhesive are not polar compounds as their log P values ranged from 2.55 to 4.64 (ChemDraw 2010). It could explain the results, since the compounds have a lower tendency to solubilise in PLA as it is the most polar polymer. In addition to this, Ecovio, which consists of a biodegradable fossil basis polymer Ecoflex® and PLA (Siegenthaler et al. 2012), showed very similar results to PE. Ecoflex is added to PLA to improve the mechanical properties of PLA, but it has been demonstrated here that it decreases the barrier properties of PLA to these compounds. Furthermore, it has been reported that compounds with hydrogen donors interact with cellulose by H-bonding interactions (Chen et al. 2005); this would explain the migration values obtained through paper as all the compounds have two hydrogen donors. In order to establish a risk assessment procedure, the strategy described below was applied (Plastics Europe 2014). When the compound is listed in the plastics regulation and the migration value is below the SML, it was considered that the compound complies with Regulation 1935/2004/EC. Nevertheless, most of the adhesive compounds are not usually present on this list. Therefore, a search for the relevant no observed effect level (NOAEL) obtained from repeat-dose toxicological studies was undertaken. To obtain the tolerable daily intake (TDI) from the NOAEL, we applied a default assessment factor of 100:

$$\text{TDI (mg kg}^{-1} \text{ body weight day}^{-1}) = \text{NOAEL/assessment factor}$$

This factor gives an additional margin to take into account the possibility that humans may be more sensitive than animals. Then, in order to obtain the self-derived SML we considered a body weight of 60 kg and that a person eats 1 kg of food per day (self-derived SML = TDI*60). Finally, when it was found that the NOAEL did not exist, the TTC approach was used instead. This methodology is based on a decision-tree approach that uses information on the molecular structure of a substance to assign the substance to one Cramer classes (Cramer et al. 1978). Each Cramer class is allocated to an exposure limit (mg/person/day) (Kroes et al. 2005, 2007; Kroes 2006). Then in order to obtain a self-derived SML, a person eating 1 kg of food per day is considered. The adhesive is formed by a polymer and additives that provide the characteristics required for its use. When the migration of an additive exceeds the SML the additive is eliminated or replaced. Since there were neither specific migration limits according to Regulation 10/2011/EU (EC 2011) nor NOAEL data for the compounds identified, the TTC was used for the risk assessment. Each Cramer class is allocated to an exposure limit corresponding to a TDI expressed as mg/person/day. Cramer class I, the least toxic class, has a TDI = 1.8 mg/person/day; Cramer class II (intermediate) has a TDI = 0.54 mg/person/day; and Cramer class III (most toxic) has a TDI = 0.09 mg/person/day.

Then we considered a person eating 1 kg of food per day. Therefore, the value of the self-derived SML is the same as the TDI, but expressed as mg kg⁻¹. The software Toxtree (IdeaconsultLtd 2011) was used for Cramer class assignation. This software assigned the Cramer classes according the decision tree developed with the Cramer rules (Cramer et al. 1978). These compounds were classified in Cramer classes II and III (see the legend to Figure 3) with self-derived SMLs of 0.54 and 0.09 mg kg⁻¹ respectively. As it can be seen in Figure 3, the migration values obtained for the surfactant polymer were higher than for the self-derived SML. As a result, it was decided to remove this surfactant from the formulation. This fact highlights the importance of the safe-design adhesive strategy followed since if the migration through the different materials in the laminates had not been studied, the surfactant would not have been replaced.

Conclusions

The work reported here highlights the need to study the risk assessment of each component of an FCM. On the one hand, it has been demonstrated that the identification of compounds in the adhesive is a crucial step, since one NIAS was found in the adhesive and migrated into the food simulant. This is very relevant since Regulation 10/2011/EU states that any potential health risk derived from an NIAS should be assessed by the manufacturer. Therefore, it implies that the identification of NIAs is essential for the FCM companies. Moreover, both biodegradable and non-biodegradable materials used to form the food-contact multilayers have been studied. The lowest migration values were found for PLA. Therefore, it has been demonstrated here that the biodegradable polymer PLA acts as functional barrier to the compounds present in the adhesive and also that the choice of the materials that formed the multilayer can be decisive since the migration values were highly dependent on the material through which the compounds have to pass. Moreover, the TTC methodology has been applied in this work to calculate a self-derived SML. One additive contained in the adhesive has been removed from the adhesive formula since its migration exceeded the SML calculated through the TTC method.

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References

- AENOR. 2001. UNE-EN 13432:2001. Envases y embalajes. Requisitos de los envases y embalajes valorizables mediante compostaje y biodegradación. Programa de ensayo y criterios de evaluación para la aceptación final del envase o embalaje. Madrid: AENORA (Asociación Española de Normalización).
- AENOR. 2004. UNE-EN-14338 (2004) AENOR. Papel y cartón para contacto alimentario. Condiciones para la determinación de la migración desde el papel y cartón utilizando óxido de polifenileno modificado (MPPO) como simulante. Madrid: AENOR (Asociación Española de Normalización).
- Ash M, Ash I. 2007. Handbook of Fillers, Extenders, and Diluents, 2nd edition. Synapse Information Resources, Inc. Available from: <http://app.knovel.com/hotlink/toc/id:kpHFED003/handbook-fillers-extenders/handbook-fillersextenders>.
- Aznar M, Vera P, Canellas E, Nerín C, Mercea P, Störmer A. 2011. Composition of the adhesives used in food packaging multilayer materials and migration studies from packaging to food. *J Mater Chem*. 21:4358–4370.
- Bradley EL, Castle L. 2006. Chemical migration from adhesives used in food-contact materials and articles. FSA project A03044. London: Food Standards Agency (FSA).
- Canady R, Lane R, Paoli G, Wilson M, Bialk H, Hermansky S, Kobiush B, Lee J-E, Llewellyn C, Scimeca J. 2013. Determining the applicability of threshold of toxicological concern approaches to substances found in foods. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*. 53:1239–1249.

Canellas E, Aznar M, Nerín C, Mercea P. 2010a. Partition and diffusion of volatile compounds from acrylic adhesives used for food packaging multilayers manufacturing. *J Mat Chem*. 20:5100–5109.

Canellas E, Nerín C, Moore R, Silcock P. 2010b. New UPLC coupled to mass spectrometry approaches for screening of non-volatile compounds as potential migrants from adhesives used in food packaging materials. *Anal Chim Acta*. 666:62–69.

Canellas E, Vera P, Domeño C, Alfaro AP, Nerín C. 2012. Atmospheric pressure gas chromatography coupled to quadrupole-time of flight mass spectrometry as a powerful tool for identification of non intentionally added substances in acrylic adhesives used in food packaging materials. *J Chromatogr A*. 1235:141–148.

Canellas E, Vera P, Nerín C. 2015a. Risk assessment derived from migrants identified in several adhesives commonly used in food contact materials. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 75:79–87.

Canellas E, Vera P, Nerín C. 2015b. UPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MSE and GC-MS identification and quantification of nonintentionally added substances coming from biodegradable food packaging. *Anal Bioanal Chem*. 407:6781–6790. ChemDraw. 2010. Version 12.0.2.1076. CambridgeSoft. [cited 2017 Apr 3]. Available from: <http://www.cambridge.com/software/overview.aspx>

Chen BL, Johnson EJ, Chefetz B, Zhu LZ, Xing BS. 2005. Sorption of polar and nonpolar aromatic organic contaminants by plant cuticular materials: role of polarity and accessibility. *Environ Sci Technol*. 39:6138–6146.

Cramer GM, Ford RA, Hall RL. 1978. Estimation of toxic hazard – a decision tree approach. *Food and Cosmetics Toxicology*. 16:255–276.

Dewhurst I, Renwick AG. 2013. Evaluation of the threshold of toxicological concern (TTC) – challenges and approaches. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol*. 65:168–177.

EC. 2004. Regulation (EC) No. 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC. *Off J Eur Union*. L338:4.

EC. 2006. Commission Regulation (EC) No 2023/2006 of 22 December 2006 on good manufacturing practice for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. *Off J Eur Union L*. 384:75–78

EC. 2011. Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. *Off J Eur Union*. L12:1–89.

Echegoyen Y, Rodríguez S, Nerín C. 2016. Nanoclay migration from food packaging materials. *Food Addit Contam A*. 33:530–539.

EFSA. 2016. Review of the threshold of toxicological concern (TTC) approach and development of new TTC decision tree. [cited 2016 Mar 10]. Available from: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/pub/1006e>

Farah S, Anderson DG, Langer R. 2016. Physical and mechanical properties of PLA, and their functions in widespread applications — a comprehensive review. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 107:367–392.

FEICA. 2016. Migration testing of adhesives intended for food contact materials Brussels [Internet]. [cited 2016 1728 E. CANELLAS ET AL. May 27]. Available from: http://www.feica.eu/documents/document/20170123155554-gup-ex-f03-010_1_feica_migration_testing_for_non-plastics.pdf

Feigenbaum A, Dole P, Aucejo S, Dainelli D, Garcia CDC, Hankemeier T, N’Gono Y, Pappaspyrides CD, Paseiro P, Pastorelli S, et al. 2005. Functional barriers: properties and evaluation. *Food Addit Contam*. 22:956–967.

Florio JJ, Miller DJ. 2004. Handbook of coatings additives. 2nd ed. Norwalk (CT): King Industries. IdeaconultLtd. 2011. Toxtree - Toxic Hazard Estimation by decision tree approach. Sofia. [cited 2011 Mar 24]. Available from: <http://toxtree.sourceforge.net/>

Karsa DR. 1990. Additives for water-based coatings. In: The Proceedings of a Symposium Organised by the North West Region of the Industrial Division of the Royal Society of Chemistry, Conference in University of Liverpool; 1988 Sep 28–29. Royal Society of Chemistry.

Koster S, Bani-Estivals MH, Bonuomo M, Bradley E, Chagnon MC, Garcia ML, Godts F, Gude T, Helling R, Paseiro-Losada P, et al. 2015. Guidance on best practices on the risk assessment of non intentionally added substances (NIAS) in food contact materials and articles. ILSI Europe Report Series. 2015:1-70.

Kroes R. 2006. The threshold of toxicological concern concept in risk assessment. *Toxicol Lett.* 164:S48–S48.

Kroes R, Kleiner J, Renwick A. 2005. The threshold of toxicological concern concept in risk assessment. *Toxicol Sci.* 86:226– 230.

Kroes R, Renwick AG, Feron V, Galli CL, Gibney M, Greim H, Guy RH, Lhuguenot JC, De Sandt J. 2007. Application of the threshold of toxicological concern (TTC) to the safety evaluation of cosmetic ingredients. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 45:2533–2562.

Ministerio español de sanidad psei. 2011. Real Decreto 847/ 2011, de 17 de junio, por el que se establece la lista positiva de sustancias permitidas para la fabricación de materiales poliméricos destinados a entrar en contacto con los alimentos. *BOE Sec I.* 164:76316–76330.

Nerin C, Alfaro P, Aznar M, Domeño C. 2013. The challenge of identifying non-intentionally added substances from food packaging materials: a review. *Anal Chim Acta.* 775:14–24.

Petrie E. 2006. Handbook of adhesives and sealants. New York (NY): McGraw-Hill Education.

Plastics Europe. 2014. Risk assesment of non-listed substances (NLS) and not-intentionally added substances (NIAS) under article 19. [cited 2014 Sep]. Available from: http://www.plasticseurope.org/documents/document/20141010141117-a_for_non_listed_substances_and_nias_under_article_19_sept_2014.pdf

Risikobewertung Bf. 2010. XXVIII. Cross-linked polyurethanes as adhesive layers for food packaging materials.

BfR Recommendations Used for Adhesives. Sandler SR, Karo W, Bonesteel J-A, Pearce EM. 1998.

Polymer synthesis and characterization. San Diego (CA): Academic Press; p. 38–40.

Sanità M. 1973. Decreto Ministeriale del 21/03/1973 Disciplina igienica degli imballaggi, recipienti, utensili, destinati a venire in contatto con le sostanze alimentari o con sostanze d'uso personale. *Gazz. Uff. Suppl. Ordin.* n° 104 del 20/04/1973.

Siegenthaler KO, Kunkel A, Skupin G, Yamamoto M. 2012. Ecoflex (R) and ecovio (R): biodegradable, performanceenabling plastics. In: *Synthetic biodegradable polymers.* Berlin: Springer-Verlag Berlin; p. 91–136. Available from: www.scifinder.org

Svagan AJ, Åkesson A, Cárdenas M, Bulut S, Knudsen JC, Risbo J, Plackett D. 2012. Transparent films based on PLA and montmorillonite with tunable oxygen barrier properties. *Biomacromolecules.* Feb;13:397–405.

Svenson. 2002. Ahesives in food contact materielas and articles. Proceedings of the Proceedings Form a Nordic Seminar; Editorial: June 2001. Copenhagen: Nordic Council of Ministers, ©2002.

Vera P, Aznar M, Mercea P, Nerín C. 2011. Study of hotmelt adhesives used in food packaging multilayer laminates. Evaluation of the main factors affecting migration to

food. *J Mater Chem.* 21:420–431.

Wypych G. 2016. *Handbook of polymers*. 2nd ed. Ontario: ChemTec Publishing; p. 92